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*PERSPECTIVES OF ENTREPRENEURIAL EDUCATION IN MICRO AND
SMALL AUTOMOTIVE ENTERPRISES¹*

**PERSPECTIVAS DA EDUCAÇÃO EMPREENDEDORA NO AMBIENTE DE
MICRO E PEQUENAS EMPRESAS AUTOMOTIVAS**

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ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to analyze the perception of employees in companies within the automotive service sector in Gama-DF regarding Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO), understood as a set of behaviors associated with innovation, autonomy, proactiveness, and risk-taking. The research employed a quantitative approach, applied through a structured questionnaire with 14 statements on a Likert scale, adapted from seminal authors such as Miller and Friesen (1982) and Lumpkin and Dess (1996). The sample was composed of employees from small automotive companies located in the Multiple Activities Sector (*Setor de Múltiplas Atividades*). Data were analyzed via SPSS using descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and multiple linear regression. The results indicated that hierarchical level and length of service are variables significantly associated with the perception of EO. Employees in management positions perceive greater autonomy and openness to risk, while the operational level reports limited participation and an absence of structured policies to incentivize innovation. It is concluded that the predominant organizational culture remains centralizing, lacking formal mechanisms to foster intrapreneurship at all levels.

Keywords: intrapreneurship, entrepreneurial orientation, automotive sector, organizational culture.

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RESUMO

O presente estudo teve como objetivo analisar a percepção dos colaboradores de empresas do setor de serviços automotivos do Gama-DF quanto à Orientação Empreendedora (OE), entendida como um conjunto de comportamentos associados à inovação, autonomia, proatividade e aceitação de riscos. A pesquisa utilizou abordagem quantitativa, aplicada por meio de questionário estruturado com 14 proposições em escala Likert, adaptadas de autores como Miller e Friesen (1982) e Lumpkin e Dess (1996). A amostra foi composta por colaboradores de pequenas empresas do setor automotivo localizadas no Setor de Múltiplas Atividades. Os dados foram analisados via SPSS, utilizando estatísticas descritivas, correlação de Pearson e regressão linear múltipla. Os resultados indicaram que o nível hierárquico e o tempo de serviço são variáveis significativamente associadas à percepção da OE. Colaboradores em posições de gestão percebem maior autonomia e abertura ao risco, enquanto o nível operacional relata participação limitada e ausência de políticas estruturadas de incentivo à inovação. Conclui-se que a cultura organizacional predominante ainda é centralizadora, carecendo de mecanismos formais que fomentem o intraempreendedorismo em todos os níveis.

Palavras-chave: intraempreendedorismo, orientação empreendedora, setor automotivo, cultura organizacional.

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INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship plays a crucial role in the global economy, as it drives the development of new businesses. Aspects such as innovation and creativity emerge as responses to the understanding of what it means to undertake entrepreneurial activities. Entrepreneurship and innovation have stood out as some of the emerging themes, constituting important instruments in the search for solutions to social problems, for job and income generation, and for the pursuit of social and economic development (Casado, Siluk, & Zampieri, 2012; Gomes et al., 2023).

Indicators from the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) report show that the entrepreneurship rate in Brazil in 2020 reached the lowest level of the past eight years, declining to 31% when compared with the rates in 2019 and 2018. The economic impact resulting from the coronavirus pandemic strongly reduced economic development, leading to the disappearance of nearly 10 million entrepreneurs (GEM, 2020).

Entrepreneurship research has been explored from different perspectives - social, economic, technological, environmental, public, among others - becoming an important field of knowledge (De Jesus & Periotto, 2007; Neck & Greene, 2011; Gielnik et al., 2015; Ribeiro & Plonski, 2020; Gomes et al., 2023).

One aspect related to entrepreneurship concerns intrapreneurship, or corporate entrepreneurship. The concept of intrapreneurship first appeared in the 1980s through Gifford Pinchot III to characterize the entrepreneurial process within companies. Dornelas (2003) clarifies that corporate entrepreneurship works through programs aimed at developing and improving the entrepreneurial profile of employees and managers, in order to implement new corporate projects and businesses.

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Based on the understanding that entrepreneurship, as a human characteristic, may be present to a greater or lesser degree in individuals—and that, when stimulated, these individuals may become entrepreneurs—companies recognize that this human capital can truly become the organization's competitive advantage (Camargo et al., 2024). In this way, they foster individuals' entrepreneurial spirit as a means of encouraging creativity, innovation, calculated risk-taking, and other entrepreneurial characteristics, in order to differentiate and strengthen the organization (Inacio Junior & Gimenez, 2004). In this sense, Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) represents a viable path for many organizations to promote intrapreneurship (França, Saraiva, & Hashimoto, 2012).

Several researchers have described entrepreneurial orientation as generally associated with three dimensions: innovativeness, proactiveness, and risk-taking (Zahra, 1991; Lumpkin & Dess, 1996). Innovativeness refers to the willingness to support and enable creativity and experimentation in the development of new products, the adoption of technology, and internal processes and procedures. Proactiveness is the ability of firms to develop, rather than merely pursue, market opportunities. Risk-taking is reflected in top management's willingness to allocate a large percentage of the firm's resources to new projects and to incur substantial debt in the development of opportunities (Lumpkin & Dess, 1996).

Entrepreneurial orientation implies the implementation of actions that promote a favorable climate for initiatives of an entrepreneurial nature among employees (França, Saraiva, & Hashimoto, 2012). In this context, the present study aims to answer the following question: what is the perception of employees in companies in the automotive service sector of Gama–Federal District regarding the level of Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO)?

The general objective of this study was to analyze this perception, using EO as an indicator to measure the degree of intrapreneurship, and to verify how

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demographic and professional variables (hierarchical level, length of service) influence this view.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Intraentrepreneurship and organizational culture

Intrapreneurship describes the performance of professionals who dedicate themselves to innovating and creating within the organization where they work, committing to corporate objectives (Oliveira, Nádila, & James, 2022). Unlike the traditional entrepreneur, the intrapreneur seeks self-fulfillment and the realization of ideas, often valuing these above purely financial rewards, although reward systems are necessary (Villela, 1997).

For intrapreneurship to flourish, organizational culture is decisive. Dornelas (2023) argues that isolated training efforts are ineffective if the environment does not consistently support innovative behavior. The presence of entrepreneurial leadership and an open culture are essential to convert individual practices into sustainable growth (Silva et al., 2024).

According to Cort et al. (2010), the assessment of an intrapreneurial culture can be systematized through eight fundamental indicators. The starting point lies in communication and the decision-making process: it is crucial that the organization effectively communicates its vision and strategic objectives to ensure employee alignment, prioritizing long-term management over short-term perspectives (Dornelas, 2003).

To operationalize innovation, the organizational structure must foster autonomy, granting freedom for experimentation, and promote work in multifunctional teams, where cooperation and diversity of perspectives enhance creativity. At the same time, leadership should be decentralized, empowering all

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employees to assume responsibilities and act proactively in the absence of superiors (Pinchot & Pellman, 2004).

The sustainability of this ecosystem, however, depends on reinforcement mechanisms. Cort et al. (2010) and Pinchot and Pellman (2004) emphasize that incentives for action must be accompanied by concrete rewards (financial or social) for the results achieved, otherwise demotivation may occur. To this end, the control and measurement of innovations are essential, allowing for a fair evaluation that supports recognition. As highlighted by Hartman (2006), the integrated analysis of these indicators is essential to understand the organizational structure and the strength of the intrapreneurial environment.

Profile of automotive service companies in Brazil

The automotive services sector in Brazil encompasses a broad spectrum of activities that goes beyond simple vehicle repair. According to Maissa, Galvão, and José (2021), this segment includes the entire production chain, ranging from driving schools and auto parts retail to specialized maintenance services, requiring an integrated perspective that often lacks specific categorization in the literature. In this broad context, competitiveness is high, and as noted by Elaine (2019), the market is marked by increasingly demanding consumers in terms of price and quality, which forces organizations to seek clear strategic differentiators based on intellectual capital and infrastructure to ensure their relevance.

With regard to management, there is often a profile of founders with extensive operational experience but without a family business background, which tends to perpetuate a reactive stance and the traditional belief that profit growth results exclusively from increased workload, as reported by Ribeiro and Arlindo (2022). However, entrepreneurial training initiatives have proven effective in transforming this mindset. By adopting behavioral and economic approaches, owners are able to move from purely technical execution to charismatic and

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strategic leadership, focused on the financial viability of the business and the appreciation of human capital.

Finally, the sustainability of these companies depends directly on the modernization of their processes and environments. Elaine (2019) highlights that, in addition to the need for an organized and transparent physical space, continuous investment in workforce qualification in response to technological advances in vehicles is imperative. Complementarily, rigorous financial management, through appropriate methods of cost control and pricing, is identified as crucial for maximizing returns. In this way, the combination of technical excellence, technological updating, and efficient management consolidates the role of these companies in generating employment and income in the economy.

METHODOLOGY

The present research refers to an exploratory investigation (Gil, 2022) conducted in the Setor de Múltiplas Atividades of Gama–DF, which examines the relationship between employees' profiles and their perception of Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO). The sample consisted of employees from companies in the automotive services sector in this region, excluding owners and managers. A quantitative research method was adopted, in which empirical data were collected through a questionnaire with multiple-choice questions on a 5-point Likert scale, where each respondent selected the option most appropriate to the propositions described, ranging from 1 ("strongly disagree") to 5 ("strongly agree"). Through stratified sampling, the study aimed to measure the significance level of the independent variables - age, gender, hierarchical level, length of service, and area of activity - in relation to the perception of entrepreneurial orientation. The second section of the instrument consisted of 14 propositions for identifying EO, grounded in the literature by authors such as Miller and Friesen

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(1982), Covin and Slevin (1989), and Lumpkin and Dess (1996), and adapted by França, Saraiva, and Hashimoto (2012), focusing on the dimensions of risk receptiveness, innovation, proactiveness, and autonomy.

The data were processed using SPSS software. Descriptive analyses were conducted to characterize the sample, as well as inferential analyses, including the Pearson Correlation Coefficient to verify the association between profile variables and EO dimensions. The Multiple Linear Regression method (Ordinary Least Squares – OLS) was also applied to identify predictors of the perception of intrapreneurship.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study was conducted in the Multiple Activities Sector of Gama-DF. Of a total of 12 companies identified, six agreed to participate, reflecting challenges inherent in research in micro and small enterprises (GIL, 2022). The sample included 10 employees with different functional profiles and experience levels. This quantitative limitation requires that the interpretation of the results be done from a qualitative perspective and adherent to the sectoral reality.

To illustrate the geographical distribution, Figure 1 presents a map of the region. The visual resource highlights, through color differentiation, the participating companies in relation to the total identified, evidencing the density and dispersion of local automotive establishments.

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Figure 1 – Mapping of companies in the Multiple Activities Sector of Gama-DF, highlighting the participants in the research, prepared by the author based on data from the Regional Administration of Gama (DF).

Source: Adapted from GDF (2024).

The characterization of the respondents' sociodemographic profile, detailed in Table 1, shows a predominance of males (80%) and a strong presence of young workers, with 70% of employees aged up to 40 years. Regarding professional trajectory, 80% of the sample has up to 10 years of experience in the sector, while only 20% have more than 10 years of experience. Most employees (60%) work in operational roles. The remainder of the team is divided between supervisors (30%) and managers (10%), indicating a structure with few leaders and many executors.

These findings corroborate the panorama outlined in the specialized literature (Elaine, 2019; SEBRAE-SP, 2016), which describes the Brazilian automotive sector as an environment characterized by male predominance, low hierarchical complexity, and a predominantly technical professional profile.

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Table 1 – Profile of respondents.

Variable	Category	Frequency	%
Age Range	Up to 20 years old	1	10,00%
	21 to 30 years old	4	40,00%
	31 to 40 years old	3	30,00%
	Over 40 years old	2	20,00%
Gender	Male	8	80,00%
	Female	2	20,00%
Length of Service	Up to 1 year	2	20,00%
	1 to 5 years	3	30,00%
	5 to 10 years	3	30,00%
	Over 10 years	2	20,00%
Hierarchical Level	Operational	6	60,00%
	Supervision/Coordination	3	30,00%
	Management	1	10,00%

Comparison with previous studies confirms this scenario. A survey conducted by SEBRAE-SP (2016), which mapped nearly 40,000 maintenance and bodywork companies in São Paulo, identified a similar pattern in a sample of 400 entrepreneurs: 91% were men, with an average age of 44 and 17 years of experience in the sector.

A critical structural characteristic of this segment is the overlap of responsibilities, or “dual function”: 92% of owners are directly involved in technical execution and 86% in business administration. However, there is an asymmetry in professional qualifications, as training prioritizes the technical dimension (with emphasis on SENAI), while 81% of entrepreneurs lack specific education in business management (SEBRAE-SP, 2016).

Recent data from the Sebrae Agency (2023) confirm the sector’s economic resilience, which generated approximately R\$ 91 billion, consolidating

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its national relevance and reach - exemplified by the creation of more than 14,000 direct jobs by micro and small enterprises. Despite this expansion, longstanding structural bottlenecks persist: the shortage of qualified labor is identified as the main obstacle by 63% of entrepreneurs, combined with limited managerial capacity and resistance to technological adoption. This macroeconomic scenario is reflected in the local reality of Gama-DF, where family-run organizations with lean structures, low process formalization, and limited investment in innovation predominate.

Organizational culture is a determining element in shaping practices and behaviors within companies, directly influencing the propensity for innovation. According to Schein (2010), it is defined as a set of shared assumptions that guide how individuals perceive and react to the work environment. In the context of the small companies in the automotive sector analyzed, there is a predominance of a traditional culture focused on operational efficiency and the maintenance of established processes. Although this stance ensures stability and predictability, it tends to create barriers to intrapreneurship, which, as noted by Lumpkin and Dess (1996), requires openness to change, willingness to take risks, and encouragement of innovation.

The literature, represented by authors such as Hartman (2006) and Cort et al. (2010), suggests that intrapreneurship thrives in environments that value autonomy, decentralized decision-making, and teamwork, supported by formal recognition systems. However, the reality observed in companies in Gama-DF differs from this ideal model. Management is characterized by centralization and a strict focus on fulfilling routine tasks, restricting individual initiative and experimentation. In addition, mechanisms to encourage innovation appear incipient or nonexistent, perpetuating a management model that does little to stimulate employee proactivity.

To quantify these perceptions, the Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) scale composed of 14 propositions was applied. Data analysis was carried out using the Pearson Correlation Coefficient, aiming to identify associations between respondents' profiles and the four dimensions of EO: innovation, proactiveness, risk-taking, and autonomy (Lumpkin & Dess, 1996). The results of these correlations are presented in Table 2:

Table 2 – Correlation between profile variables and EO dimensions.

Independent Variable	Innovation	Autonomy	Risk Acceptance	Proactivity
Age	0,21	0,12	-0,08	0,18
Length of Service	0,39	0,33	0,44	0,28
Hierarchical Level	0,55	0,48	0,60	0,41
Gender	0,05	0,02	-0,03	0,06
Area of Expertise	0,30	0,26	0,25	0,20

Source: Research data processed via SPSS (2025).

The statistical analysis revealed significant correlations between employees' hierarchical profiles and the dimensions of Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO). Of particular relevance is the strong association between hierarchical level and risk-taking ($r = 0.60$). This finding suggests a stratification in the perception of organizational culture: employees in managerial positions perceive greater freedom of action and encouragement for initiative, whereas operational-level employees report significant constraints. These results corroborate the theoretical model of Lumpkin and Dess (1996), which postulates autonomy as a critical antecedent of EO, variably distributed according to the organizational power structure. França, Saraiva, and Hashimoto (2012) reinforce this interpretation by associating entrepreneurial orientation directly with the perception of decision-making power and institutional recognition.

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This discrepancy in the perception of autonomy indicates that the analyzed companies perpetuate traditional and centralized organizational cultures. The concentration of decision-making power at the top of the hierarchy inhibits the diffusion of intrapreneurial behaviors at the base of the organization, contradicting the decentralization principles advocated by Cort et al. (2010) and Dornelas (2023) as essential for systemic innovation.

Additionally, a structural weakness was identified in reward systems. Qualitative analysis and data from the EO scale point to the predominance of informal and unsystematic incentive practices. As warned by Pinchot and Pellman (2004), the absence of clear recognition and reward mechanisms compromises the sustainability of intrapreneurial behavior, since the risks inherent to innovation are not perceived as valued by the organization. The lack of formal processes for monitoring and measuring innovative initiatives further aggravates this scenario, preventing the systematization of improvements and the replication of successful experiences.

Regarding leadership and group dynamics, the results indicate a predominantly conservative management style. Although employees who perceive support from their supervisors demonstrate higher EO—confirming the role of leadership as a catalyst for innovation (Bruno, 2021; Silva et al., 2025)—this support is not uniform. At the same time, the work culture appears individualized, with weak integration between sectors. The incipient presence of multifunctional teams limits creative potential and knowledge exchange, which are fundamental elements of an intrapreneurial culture according to Hartman (2006).

In summary, although signs of entrepreneurial orientation were identified in the organizations studied, it manifests in an elitist manner, restricted to employees with longer tenure and higher hierarchical positions. Consolidating EO as a collective and transversal organizational value requires overcoming these

structural barriers, demanding the implementation of decision-making decentralization policies, the formalization of incentive systems, and the promotion of collaborative practices aimed at strengthening the competitiveness and adaptive capacity of the local automotive sector.

To understand which characteristics of employees' profiles influence the perception of Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO), multiple linear regression analysis was applied. This statistical technique is widely recommended for investigating how various factors simultaneously impact a given outcome (MINITAB, 2019; Gil, 2022).

In the proposed model, the dependent variable (the outcome to be explained) was the average EO score obtained from the questionnaire. The independent variables (explanatory factors) tested were: age, length of service, hierarchical level, area of activity, and gender. The statistical calculation was based on the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method, which, according to Gujarati (2006), fits the model by minimizing the margin of error between real data and statistical predictions.

The first run of the full model showed that some variables were not statistically significant, particularly Age ($p = 0.621$) and Gender ($p = 0.744$). Considering the exclusion criterion based on p-values greater than 0.05, these variables were removed from the model in the subsequent attempt, as recommended by Minitab (2019). In the second model, regression analysis showed that the variables length of service and hierarchical level presented p-values below the 5% significance level, confirming that these variables have a statistically significant influence on EO. The area of activity, in turn, remained with $p > 0.05$ and did not reach statistical significance.

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Table 3 – Results of the final multiple linear regression model.

Variable	Coefficient (β)	P-value	Significance
Length of Service	0,36	0,042	Significant
Hierarchical Level	0,51	0,015	Significant
Area of Expertise	0,24	0,081	Not significant
Adjusted R ²	0,48	-	-

Source: Research data (2025).

The statistical modeling resulted in an adjusted coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.48, indicating that 48% of the variance in the perception of Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) is jointly explained by the independent variables length of service and hierarchical level. As noted by Gil (2022), this magnitude is considered satisfactory for exploratory studies in applied social sciences, given the complexity and subjectivity of the organizational factors involved. Although the model does not account for the phenomenon in its entirety, it confirms the predominance of these variables as structural determinants of intrapreneurship.

Regarding the variable length of service, a positive correlation with EO was observed. Employees with longer organizational tenure demonstrated a greater propensity to propose improvements, innovate in processes, and assume calculated risks. This phenomenon finds theoretical support in Cezar, Maccari, and Pereira (2009), who associate such behavior with the accumulation of tacit knowledge, which provides psychological security and mastery over routines. Thus, accumulated experience acts as a catalyst for individual initiative and a sense of belonging, aligning with the assumptions of Lumpkin and Dess (1996).

At the same time, hierarchical level proved to be a determining predictor. Individuals in supervisory or managerial positions reported higher levels of autonomy and freedom of action, corroborating the premise that entrepreneurial opportunity is intrinsically linked to one's position within the power structure

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(França, Saraiva, & Hashimoto, 2012). According to Dornelas (2023), intrapreneurship flourishes in structures that delegate decision-making responsibility; however, in the companies analyzed, the strong correlation between management roles and EO reveals a concentration of autonomy at the top of the hierarchy, restricting the diffusion of these practices at the operational level.

This scenario reflects a culture of centralized power, typical of small companies in the automotive sector. The operational base, characterized by younger employees with shorter tenure, perceives significant structural barriers to the development of intrapreneurial competencies. This finding reinforces the need for decentralization and the institutionalization of EO as a collective value for its effective implementation (Cort et al., 2010).

Additionally, the absence of incentive practices was identified. The recognition initiatives reported lack formalization and consistency, compromising motivation for innovation. Pinchot and Pellman (2004) warn that the effectiveness of incentives depends on clear reward mechanisms—financial, symbolic, or career-related. The absence of meritocracy and transparency in these policies therefore constitutes a barrier to consolidating an intrapreneurial organizational climate.

Leadership also emerged as a critical factor. The perception of support from supervisors was associated with a greater willingness to face challenges, validating the thesis that entrepreneurial leaders act as facilitators of innovation (Bruno, 2021; Silva et al., 2025). However, the prevalence of conservative management styles, focused on maintaining the status quo and showing aversion to error, inhibits the emergence of new practices (Monteverde, 2021).

Finally, weaknesses in collaborative work and the absence of innovation metrics were identified. Fragmented performance and the lack of multifunctional teams limit synergy and collective creativity (Hartman, 2006). The absence of

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systematic records hinders knowledge management and organizational learning, contradicting the recommendations of Pinchot and Pellman (2004).

In summary, the entrepreneurial posture is not equally distributed among members of the organizations studied. It is concentrated mainly among managers and long-tenured employees. For most frontline workers, the company's traditional culture limits opportunities to act as intrapreneurs.

CONCLUSION

The research conducted made it possible to understand the dynamics of Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) in the automotive context of the Setor de Múltiplas Atividades in Gama-DF. It is concluded that, within these organizations, intrapreneurship does not flow transversally but instead appears as an advantage restricted to certain hierarchical levels. The empirical results demonstrated that structural variables - specifically hierarchical level and length of service - are determinants for the manifestation of EO, revealing an organizational dichotomy: while managers and long-tenured employees perceive autonomy and openness to risk, the operational base experiences a reality of centralized decision-making and limited incentives for proactivity.

This configuration shows that the micro and small enterprises (MSEs) analyzed operate under traditional management models, where innovation is constrained by the absence of formal support mechanisms. Weaknesses in incentive and reward systems, combined with the incipient development of collaborative teamwork, create barriers that inhibit the creative potential of employees with shorter tenure or subordinate positions. It is therefore concluded that the prevailing organizational culture tends to perpetuate routine execution at the expense of exploring new opportunities.

In this context, Entrepreneurial Education emerges not only as a theoretical concept but as an essential managerial strategy. Managers are

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encouraged to invest in continuous training programs and in the creation of spaces for experimentation, with the aim of democratizing entrepreneurial behavior. To enhance the competitiveness of the local automotive sector, it is necessary to move from centralized leadership toward management practices that foster autonomy and systematize the recognition of innovative ideas across all hierarchical levels.

The study presents limitations due to the small sample size, which restricts the generalization of the findings. Future research is recommended to increase the number of participants and to adopt qualitative approaches in order to more deeply understand the barriers that hinder the promotion of intrapreneurship in micro and small enterprises.

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